

POPULAR ARCHITECTURE AMONG VERNACULAR AND ERUDITE CONTEXTS

Pedro Fonseca Jorge

CES – Centro de Estudos Sociais – Universidade de Coimbra

Abstract: In our present and contemporary architectural context abstractionism has become the face of a theoretical crisis where words seem to be the main form of communicating visually incomprehensible shapes. Therefore we need to search for a more figurative architecture based upon our landscape's features, making it necessary to proceed to Typological researches about our built surroundings. Rural housing has been a forgotten research field, as people tend to pay more attention to dense fabrics, but that doesn't mean that heritage can't be found in rural contexts. In this way to study rural architecture is to include Types of architecture that may or may not include features from other cultures than their own. This paper will try to define the features that define these Types, according to the contexts of Vernacular architecture (when there are no more references than the culture where it is produced) and Popular Architecture (where Signs or Significances have been brought from different contexts, being them Vernacular, Popular or Erudite).

Keywords: Popular Architecture, Vernacular architecture, Erudite architecture.

1. Introduction

This article is based upon the need to create a lexicon in the "Architecture without Architects" domain in order to distinguish different types of interventions included in this typology. Among these types we can define a first one where there is no contamination from cultures outside the one where the type is created, opposed to another kind of "architectless" architecture that inherits signs beyond its cultural borders. Despite this fact, we still can't define this type as "Erudite", not only because it remains based upon popular knowledge, but because its influences can range from erudite architecture to other cultural contexts defined as vernacular or popular – or "without architects".

The need to define this type of architecture – without a single author, but with external influences – was felt in previous researches, where, for example, the Rural Housing Type from the surroundings of the city of Alcobaça, Portugal, was surveyed and its models collected. Alcobaça's City Hall and its archives was the elected source to support the proposed research, focused on the year of 1961: not also this was the year where the city hall's records began (although there were previous documentation, lost nowadays), but this date also corresponded to the year where the book "Arquitetura Popular em Portugal" (Popular Architecture in Portugal) was published.

2. The reference

This book, commonly referred as the "Inquiry", was a national survey promoted by the Portuguese National Architects' Syndicate, where various teams of architects joined together to collect information about rural Portuguese architecture, which its authors believed to be disappearing gradually. Roughly the same reasons that lead Bernard Rudofsky to publish "Architecture without Architects" in 1964: industrialization, architecture's internationalization (we were already in a period where the Modernist dogmas were being criticized), the abandonment of the countryside in search of better living conditions in the cities, etc.

In Portugal, the country was "divided" in several regions, each one with an assigned team that would research the architectural types in risk of disappearing. Different criteria among the teams about what was really "popular" architecture, for instance, lead to a survey not always coherent, but still this book was fundamental as an architecture manifesto, but also political statement.

The Portuguese dictatorial regime had been supporting for a long time an idea of a Portuguese "traditional" architecture that had little in common with the built reality. The porpoise was to portrait Portugal as a wealthy country where middle-class families lived in "typical" houses in a bucolical countryside (imagined models, conceived by architects, nothing more than a sum of decorative elements over a common house model). Through this (false) picturesque scenario the struggling under-privileged classes were obliterated from the "official" national portrait.

Portuguese architects saw in this survey the opportunity to research popular housing types, but also a way to show own the Portuguese population really lived: in poor and small houses, with little or no salubrity at all, although these where the houses that defined our territory. And, obviously, this research also proved that rather than a "Portuguese house", there were different types of houses in Portugal, according to the economy, climate and topography of a certain region (that is why the book was called "Popular Architecture in Portugal", and not "Portuguese Popular Architecture"). And all with the dictatorship's money, since these was a government subsidized research.

Apparently, as the National Architects Syndicate predicted, the Types and Models presented in the book were part of a legacy that was in danger of disappearing, since nowadays it's almost impossible to find them in our built landscape. Mainly because those housing Types were substituted by more recent ones, sometimes carrying outer influences beyond their initial cultural background.

3. The (Un)Avoidable Reality

Architecture nowadays struggles with the need to search for physical references for its proposals, as it becomes more and more a question of image and star system. The search for originality (just for the sake of public visibility) has lead architecture to a self-referenced world where it's only understood by architects themselves. The necessary theoretical support is, in most cases, a "crutch" for the design itself, the reverse process of the "ethical" creating procedure, were, basically, an idea leads to a shape.

This is partially cause by the progressive disappearance of the Sign and Significant in architecture: the references that are intended among the built, natural and cultural surroundings of the architectural object are often supported only by a theoretical discourse (the Significance) that as no match in its formal counterpart. Quality in architecture thus becomes a matter of trust rather than a verifiable feature, and, as consequence, Ethics becomes the solely way to qualify architecture.

Therefore there is a need in contemporary architecture to search for more visible references, beyond the boundaries of Contemporary Architecture itself. And, therefore, this can be the opportunity to adopt a posture where we can search for references, as architects and producers of the built environment, in the existing architectural legacy, thus justifying a new approach to "architecture without architects". Synonymous of adopting a "new realism"¹, based upon a Past that is constantly evolving.

The Alcobaça District was poorly documented in the Portuguese inquiry, an other sources had to be used in order to achieve further information about the region's vernacular or popular architecture.

As we said above, the City Hall's archives were a useful resource, since the required permission

¹ Fonseca Jorge, P. (2013), "Post-minimal-contextualism-critical-modernism Reality" [Conferência], I Congreso Arquitectura Universidad Investigación y Sociedad, Departament de Projectes Arquitectonics (ETSAB). Available at: http://www.academia.edu/1751876/Post-minimal-contextualism-critical-modernism_Reality [02.2013]

to build was given after the presentation of the drawings of the intended house. And also, the older requests (as previous ones had been lost) corresponded to the year of 1961, the same were the book "Arquitetura Popular em Portugal" was published.

The information that composed this licence request was very poor: the name of the owner, the village's name and plans and façades of the house. There was no specific reference to the site, for example, or even a section of the house. Nevertheless this information was enough to trace the spatial matrix of a popular architecture Type that seemed to be very common in the area. At this point we must determine what we define as a Type and Model: "in architectural terms, it's the conceptual structure, the spatial matrix that exists, even with different formal solutions, in a certain number of buildings previous selected with a specific goal in mind"² (that goal being a Typology: a researched based upon those selected Types, according to the same source). A Model (...) is the finished object, a building that can be repeated (...)³.

As the present investigation began there was a "hidden" will to search for a specific Type of single family houses that defines, even today, part of Alcobaça's built landscape. This could a Type that would define the rural architecture of the district, as it was lacking further information about the subject. This house presented some constant typological features that included a rectangular plan, two-sloped roof and a symmetrical façade with a front door and a window in each side.

We may add that by referring a Type based upon an empirical observation of the landscape we are also assuming that it can also be related to aesthetic and formal features, even if we couldn't relate it to a specific spatial solution, although further digging, as mentioned, in Alcobaça's archives, proved otherwise.

Figure 1: author's photos and drawings of Alcobaça' rural house models nowadays.

However the archives revealed two kinds of predominant Types (that corresponded each to about 50% of the requests), very different, for instance, from those present in the 1961's inquiry by the National Architects Syndicate: the first of those Types was the above mentioned symmetrical house, a characteristic that was "transported" inside. The main door leads to a central hall giving access to four rooms with the same size. Among them the kitchen was only recognizable by the fact that there was an extra door leading to the house's courtyard and a fireplace (simple rectangle in the floor plans). But, although outside there was always the same symmetry, a great number of models had a different layout inside, where, for example, the hall was added to the living room).

² Barata Fernandes, F. (1999) Transformação e Permanência na Habitação Portuense – As formas da Casa na Forma da Cidade, (2ª ed.), Faculdade de Arquitectura da Universidade do Porto, 1999, ISBN 10: 972-9483-37-X.

³ Idem

Figure 2: A Model from the Type found during the investigation in Alcobaça's city hall, which corresponded to approximately to half of the licenced houses in 1961.

The other housing Type was the complete opposite: it had an elongated floor plan, perpendicular to the road, with an asymmetrical façade: the entrance door was drawn back along one of the windows, and the two slop roof was oriented sideways. Inside there was a narrow corridor in the middle of the house that lead to all the rooms, each one with a specific dimension that corresponded to a specific use: a Modern solution revealed by its hierarchy and functional character.

Figure 3: Example of the other common housing Type in 1961, with its asymmetrical character and inner distribution.

We must keep in mind that the information about these Models and Types was scarce: its orientation was not referred, for instance, and even the project's author wasn't mentioned. In fact, it's probable that the author wasn't even a technician, as Portugal had a very small number of architects in this period (in 1973 there were only 500, and mostly lived and worked in Lisbon or Oporto, thus creating the "need" to approve a law that allowed other technicians to design architectural projects, until recently... but that's another story). That might explain some incoherent projects were, for instance, you had to enter the bathroom (a "new" feature) in order to get to the kitchen or a room, as the author had no skills to "create", only to "copy" pre-existing models.

Nevertheless, the main question that arouses, beyond its authorship, relates to its cultural context: although we can recognize in them some external influences that determine shape and spatial solution (Classical or Modern), these aren't still Erudite examples of architecture, or something that has been created in an academic context so to speak. It's rather the appropriation and adaptation of known models, from erudite or urban contexts, to a rural way of living. They are part of other field of interest in Architecture, commonly (and uncritically) designated as Vernacular or Popular, since, among other features, its author is anonymous, or a whole community rather than a single one (to quote the most common). So, we must pose the following question: since the book "Arquitetura Popular em Portugal" was about "Popular" architecture, why weren't these models present in this inquiry?

Figure 4: Here we can compare the models collected by the author (above and below) and those presented in "Arquitetura Popular em Portugal" (center). It's important to refer that, although there is no reference about Alcobaça's rural architecture in the above mentioned book, older people refer that the Model presented in the middle (with a small and enclosed porch in the entrance), typical from Leiria (in the same geographical region of Portugal), was somehow common in the studied area.

4. "The intolerable miscegenation of architecture"

Since one of the main purposes of the 1961 survey was to gather information about the popular architecture models that were in danger of disappearing, we can point that, obviously, that wasn't the case of those present in the archives (since they were being built precisely at that time). Its very common presence the built landscape (probably beyond the borders of the studied area) made it, by the opposite, the "most vulgar architecture, houses with nothing in particular, all the same"⁴.

These houses were "misdeeds" in the popular rural landscape, in which models imported from a "cultured" context (the city), inadequate in this new background, were intentionally ignored. In fact, those responsible for the recollection of models were sceptic about these "hybrid" solutions (considering the aesthetical solution, but also the constructive one, as concrete was mixed with traditional building techniques, for instance).

Therefore there was a biased tendency, as the Models that didn't fit in the 2nd generation Modernist portuguese architects intended image of a romantic, though rational, popular architecture, capable of reinventing Modern Architecture.

However, the mere fact that these models exist, doesn't that make them important enough to be studied, since they were born under a specific social and cultural context? And even if they don't "fit" in the intended category of pure and uninfluenced rural architecture, rather than just consider them as "misdeeds", isn't there a specific category where we can fit them? In other words: the only admissible architectonic languages are the ones that oppose pure academic thought and "innocent" popular thinking? Isn't there anything in between that can link these two Types of architecture? After all, if we can admit that Modern Architecture searched for vernacular or popular signs to evolve its own language and symbols (in what, among other categories, Kenneth Frampton defined as "critical regionalism"⁵), isn't it probable that the opposite process occurred as well?

It's under these premises that this article evolves to second part where there is an attempt to contextualize these two "kinds" of "people's" architecture (the word "popular" is intentionally avoided) according to its interactions with different social and cultural contexts. And, according to the encountered dissimilarities, we will try to define a specific context for "Vernacular" and "Popular" architecture.

5. Vernacular Architecture

We begin under the assumption that using the terms "Vernacular" and "Popular" in a undifferentiated manner can be a mistake, and that the differentiation between these two meanings it's essential to create a consistent lexicon among scholars.

Common sense tells us that both contexts defined by "Vernacular" and "Popular" are referred to practical and empirical attitudes towards architecture and building techniques, having not a single author, but an entire community that shares knowledge in a restrict cultural and spatial context (commonly considered as "rural").

However to "belong" to a circumscribed area can be manifested in several ways, as many as the ones that define a building: its construction process, the obtained shape, the resulting image and

⁴ Leal, J (2011, Maio). Entre o Vernáculo e o Híbrido: a partir do Inquérito à Arquitectura Popular em Portugal, Joelho #2: Intersecções: antropologia e arquitectura, Revista de cultura Arquitectónica, pp. 72. ISSN: 0874-6168

⁵ Frampton, K. (1996), Historia critica de la arquitectura moderna. Editorial Gustavo Gili, S.A. pp. 318-332, ISBN 84-252-1628-1

Frampton, K. (1983) *Towards a critical regionalism: six points for an architecture of resistance*. In, Foster, H. (ed). Postmodern Culture. London; Pluto Press. pp.16-30.

the anthropological space.

5.1. The Frontier

Originally the term "Vernacular" is given, in linguistic terms, to a language that is spoken inside a culturally well-defined community. Its opposite is "Vehicular"⁶, a language common to several groups, used among different communities or according to larger borders.

This definition of "Vernacular", when used in the architecture discipline, it's manifested through buildings that are immediately identified with a specific place, since they had its origins according to the physical and sociological needs of a restricted group of dwellers, the use of materials circumscribed to closed frontier and its adequacy to its geographical agents.

There is a logic of "permanence" that defines the group, opposed to its mobility beyond its physical and intellectual borders. As a result, the architectural Type defining the individual and communal habitat (building and urban image) evolves slowly as it has no outer influences and still complies with the population's needs. Changes, small but unstoppable, are based upon the community's experience. Every new proposed Type will have the previous one, altered throughout time, according to a process that we define as "tradition".

The lack of information exchange (due to referred boundaries) influences the Type's static nature and its evolving character, as opposed to a Type that is substituted due to the input of new information about construction, materials and shapes.

The slowed process of acquiring information can be due to sociocultural motives, but also to geographical and political boundaries. The impossibility to overpass these frontiers defines the use of local resources: material, constructive methods, being these defined by its simplicity, in order to be able to become common knowledge among the community, thus leading to similar Models in terms of shape and use.

The utilitarian character of Vernacular Architecture doesn't mean that Signs and Significants are absent, only that the used Signs share the same Signification (Meaning), because they are associated to a common belief.

5.2. The Type

Since we can relate an Architectural Type to a specific geographic/cultural area, we can say that that region has a Vernacular Architectural Type that defines it. Evolution is part of this Type, as Tradition makes it evolve through a slow and closed self-referenced process. But as Francisco Barata Fernandes⁷ puts it, a Type's evolution is only possible until a certain point, where the introduced changes detract the initial concept. Above that we have to talk about a different Type, with specific features.

This evolving process depends of many things, although contained inside well define barriers, so we can't truly define the length of a certain Type, although Christian Lassure argues that it has a life span of about "10 to 100 years"⁸. The reasons behind this analysis failed to be presented, though.

5.3 Tradition

⁶ Magnan, G. Architecture Vernaculaire au Mali. <http://users.swing.be/geoffroy.magnan/mali/>, [01.2013]

⁷ Fernandes, F. B. (1999). *Transformação e Permanência na Habitação Portuguesa: as formas da casa na forma da cidade*. Porto: FAUP Publicações, ISBN 10: 972-9483-37-X.

⁸ Lassure, C. (1993) *L'architecture vernaculaire de la France*, in *L'architecture vernaculaire*, 17, <http://www.pierreseche.com/VAFrance.html>, [01.2013]

The empirical definition of tradition leads us to believe in "immutability" and "stagnation", often linked to a romantic image of the past. However tradition allows change, although not a radical one because its physical and intellectual space is limited. Therefore there isn't a clear scission with established knowledge and newly acquired one, but when change occurs (induced by need) it's encompassed among common knowledge, without substituting it. There isn't a conscious will to maintain something permanently, only knowledge that evolves accordingly to the imposed physical and cultural boundaries.

Therefore Tradition is a noun that qualifies any kind of relations that are recognized between established and new, according to one's needs. The Type's characteristics that linger are those that are still able to correspond to real needs; the ones that are replaced are those that no longer fulfil new physical, but also sociological needs.

We can conclude that Tradition is a term that is abusively used when referred to features and circumstances where the Type's immutability is artificially sustained, no longer corresponding to the user's expectations. We can relate this concept to Vernacular Architecture, but also to all other Types of Architecture.

5.4. Absent concepts

There are other definitions that are commonly linked to Vernacular Architecture, though wrongly. The notion of Primitive is one of those characteristics, and we can relate that misconception with the use of Western Culture as a counterpoint to our investigations. There are communities that have, comparatively, ancestral ways of living. But Distance, Frontier, Type and Tradition do not necessarily mean a faraway past, although suggested by Vernacular Architecture's image: its materials and building techniques are no longer in use in our society, currently replaced by industrialized products that cross numerous borders.

However this commonly accepted image of restricted material and techniques are questioned by some, as for Amos Rapoport⁹ who admits the existence of standardization in Vernacular Architecture, in a way that the Type maintains its features and its building process is simple enough to be able to be applied by all community's members. The notion of "standardization" will be addressed again forwardly as we will try to define Popular Architecture.

Rurality

Rurality is also commonly associated to vernacular architecture, but this type of architecture can be related to other urban settlements, though less obvious. The city is commonly identified as a place of commerce and exchange of goods, but also knowledge: it's easy for a type to evolve according to outer influences from other architectural cultures, sometimes easier to be replaced altogether from imported models and its types.

In well preserved contexts it's still possible though to identify a city through a precise built landscape defined by a similar image, shape and building process: a specific Type to a specific place. This kind of coherence it's more easily identified in a rural context because evolution is slower and typological substitution rarer. Therefore vernacular architecture is frequently mistaken with something Primitive, the same way that Permanence is mistaken with Tradition. But, as it was said before, Tradition is related with Evolution, and it is wrong to relate a slower evolution with permanence or stagnation.

6. Popular Architecture

Therefore, is there a disciplinary field where we can fit something as "Popular Architecture"? Among the researches made in the field of "architecture without architects" their authors felt no

⁹ Rapoport, A. (1972) *Vivienda e Cultura*, Barcelona, Gustavo Gili, 1972

need to differentiate Vernacular and Popular, probably because there was no further research about rural architecture after the "Arquitetura Popular em Portugal" book's publication. Martins Barata¹⁰ uses the term vernacular, José Manuel Fernandes e Maria de Lourdes Janeiro¹¹ prefer vernacular.

Jane Pieplow¹² is one of the rarest researchers that try to differentiate the two words and its disciplinary field, as she refers that in a "Popular" context it's impossible to identify a single source (and a single period) for its features, even if these can be determined individually. The lack of tradition is therefore a consequence, non-existing in the vernacular context (which makes it sometimes difficult to date its models). She also refers that there are different "styles" adopted among different Types, something that we can relate to an erudite context (as an influence).

According to the above mentioned features we can conclude that many of the architectural models presented in the "Inquiry" can be classified as "Vernacular" and not "Popular" (being "Popular" a Type that we will try to define later). Especially since, as it was said in the previous paragraphs, those models corresponded to specific criteria in order to support a predetermined idea that excluded the models found in the 1961 Alcobça's Municipality archives. But it's also true that these models fail to comply with the whole definition of "Vernacular", as they add new features that can relate them to a whole new Type in People's Architecture.

But why should we use the term "Popular", if it has been used since long ago, in the lexicon of "architecteless architecture" scholars as a synonym of "Vernacular"? If we use the same criteria used by Geoffrey Magnan (namely the word's original semantics) we achieve at a concept of "Popular" (in the Portuguese Language) as something "belonging to the people; people's own; used by or frequently associated with the people; (...) that appeals to the greatest number of people; that enjoys the favour of the public (...)"¹³. Or, in the English Language, "well liked (...); accepted, favourite, approved; in favour (...)"¹⁴. As for "People", in Portuguese ("Povo"): "set of individuals that have the same origin, the same language, traditions, manners, a common cultural and historical past (...) occupying a particular territory (...)"¹⁵; in English: "(...) nation, public, community, subjects, population, (...) folk (...)"¹⁶.

If in these definitions isn't referred a clear geographical boundary, we can still focus our attention in the fact that what is Popular is appealing to the People, common among those and democratic. In other words, depends upon a choice, made without the objection of others, implying the existence of more than one option. Which is very important if we take into account that "Vernacular" means (in Portuguese) "(something) which preserves the original state, without loanwords; genuine, pure (...)"¹⁷.

¹⁰ Barata, M. (1989) *Arquitetura Popular Portuguesa*. Edição da Direcção de Relações Internacionais de Filatelia dos Correios e Telecomunicações de Portugal, 1998, ISBN 972-9127-03-4

¹¹ Fernandes, J. M. & Janeiro, M. L. (1991) *Arquitetura Vernácula na Região Saloia, enquadramento na área Atlântica*, 1ª ed, Instituto de Cultura e Língua Portuguesa, 1991, ISBN 972-566-130-3

¹² Pieplow, J. (2006: May) All-american family houses: Fallon's architectural styles, in *Focus*, Vol.11, <http://www.ccmuseum.org/InFocus/Architecture/architecture1.htm>, [05.2006]

¹³ "Popular" (2013), In *Dicionário da Língua Portuguesa*, Dicionários Editora, Porto Editora, 2011, page 1266, ISBN 978-972-0-01564-8 (my translation)

¹⁴ "Popular" (2013), In *Collins Colour Pocket Thesaurus*, 3rd Edition 2004, HarperCollins Publishers, page 423, ISBN 0-00-716263-4

¹⁵ "Povo" (2013), In *Dicionário da Língua Portuguesa*, Dicionários Editora, Porto Editora, 2011, ISBN 978-972-0-01564-8, page 1274, (my translation)

¹⁶ "People" (2013), In *Collins Colour Pocket Thesaurus*, 3rd Edition 2004, HarperCollins Publishers, page 406, ISBN 0-00-716263-4

¹⁷ "Vernáculo" (2013), In *Dicionário da Língua Portuguesa*, Dicionários Editora, Porto Editora, 2011, page 1637,

6.1. Introducing new knowledge and cultures

If we apply these concepts to Architecture we arrive at two different and well defined fields of knowledge where two very different Types can be found. In this case we will consider that "loanwords" can't be applied to political boundaries, since these are volatile and incapable of containing the people's cultural expression. Therefore the concept of "foreigner" will be assumed as something that stands outside the vernacular culture of a given place.

When considering the notion of "border" we will have to consider this type of limit as something with two "sides", and its trespass as having consequences for both sides (and cultures). The cultural and technological exchange is inevitable, between different vernacular architectures, or among vernacular, popular and erudite architectures. We can say that none of the different cultures remains immune to its "opposite", but in the Vernacular's specific case it's harder to be indifferent to the novelties and originalities of "new" cultures and its architecture. As for the Erudite context being able to absorb data from Vernacular and Popular architecture, that can and should be the subject-matter of a study apart from the present one: each has its own specificities, both important).

Therefore if we consider the presence of "foreign" features among Vernacular Architecture's models, we possibly can justify a change in the Type itself: Vernacular becomes Popular, in the specific case of the above mentioned Types, with characteristics imported from (an) Erudite Architecture.

If we accept the above premises we can establish a cause and effect relation, where a Type succeeds to another, and where Vernacular and Popular are assumed as moments of an historical path whose limits may vary according to region, culture, frontiers, etc. Some scholars have tried to establish a precise moment for this process, like João Vieira Caldas that defines "the period after the 18th century as the moment when the frontier between Popular and Erudite was diluted"¹⁸, while between 1550 and 1800 architecture was made of similar Types.

The formal and sociological context of Vieira Caldas' context (between more modest houses and mansion-houses where erudite and rural borders are tenuous¹⁹) portrays an well-defined historical moment: the one where the precise studied Types occur). Therefore it should be considered as an additional reference to this paper, but not an example that can be extended to all Popular Architecture manifestations.

In our present attempt to define "popular", based upon the typological study of the 1961 Alcobaça's District rural house, we can notice that there is a bigger expertise in construction processes where new material replace the ones identified in the "Inquiry". These first models were made in earth, while the more recent ones found in the Alcobaça archives were made in small stones with earth as mortar while only the wedges and lintels used bigger solid stones. These were still local materials, and the reasons the building procedures have changed are not clear (though obviously linked to the change of housing type), but these motives could (and should) be the purpose of parallel researches.

ISBN 978-972-0-01564-8 (my translation)

¹⁸ Caldas, J. V. (1999), *A casa rural nos arredores de Lisboa no séc. XVIII*, Faculdade de Arquitectura da Universidade do Porto, 1999, ISBN 972-9483-31-0 (my translation)

¹⁹ Idem

Figure 5: The juxtaposition of decorative patterns over common tectonic elements (jambs and lintels) reveals the introduction of erudite signs over a Model that, through its spatial solution, already reveals external influences from its "own" cultural background. The pattern shown above was very common among these Type of houses, as for the windows/doors dimensions, so we can already talk about standardization in Popular Architecture.

However, in most cases, making use of Signs of an Erudite Architecture is more often related to an aesthetic aim (without its Significance) where popular communities tried to relate themselves to an upper social background. This kind of attempt would also be identified in Emigrants' Houses, especially from France, who alluded to an also popular French architecture, and consisted to an attempt from his tenants to detach themselves from the misery they left behind when they decided to emigrate: to this poverty was associated the Type identified in the "Inquiry"²⁰.

But to this phenomenon we can mention a very interesting study about emigrant houses in the

²⁰ Leal, J (2011, Maio). *Entre o Vernáculo e o Híbrido: a partir do Inquérito à Arquitectura Popular em Portugal*, in Joelho #2: Intersecções: antropologia e arquitectura, Revista de cultura Arquitectónica, pp. 12. ISSN: 0874-6168

north of Portugal (Vila Praia de Âncora), where the authors identified more actors in the process of creating these sometimes hybrid models between portuguese and French popular architecture: sometimes even the portuguese designers (but not architects) to whom these designs were ordered²¹.

6.2. The Type and its deviations

Typological diversity is one of main features that may distinguish Vernacular from Popular, once Tradition acts as a regulator, associated with the existence of well-defined cultural borders: usually a single architectonic Type is "allowed". Once these conditions disappear "architecture without architects" becomes free to adopt new Types, but also to make them evolve and change according to the topological, morphological and climacteric needs that characterize the place that "imports" the Type.

So, in the geographical and temporal lapse we are studying, architecture, while not being Vernacular, is also not Erudite, since the classical reference it's not used academically, but in a critically manner: besides the main volume that retains features like orthogonality and symmetry, further expansions are added through time in an irregularly fashion and adapting themselves to the topography.

The collected Models, who were presented to the City Hall's authorities only in their initial shape, something like its "first Module", were very similar, externally speaking, with features that were constant among them: rectangular shape, two-slopped roof oriented to the main façade, symmetrical elevations, etc. However, while maintaining the same Type it was possible to identify in the Models different spatial matrixes, who can lead us to believe that is possible to identify "Sub-types", which while maintaining the initial features, differentiate themselves through others. Therefore, in Popular Architecture we can admit that more than the "spatial matrix" defended by Francisco Barata, a Type, in architecture, can also be identified through shapes and aesthetic features, mainly those that lead to the present research.

²¹ Villanova, Roselyne; de, Leite, Carolina; Raposo, Isabel; foreward from Portas, Nuno; drawings by Góis, Luísa e Raposo, Isabel; fotografias de Pierre Gaudin e Isabel Raposo (1994). Casas de sonhos: emigrantes construtores no Norte de Portugal, Lisboa: Salamandra 1994. ISBN: 972-689-083-7

Figure 6: Some examples of Models collected in the City Hall's archives, that although belong to a formal similar Type, have different spatial matrixes (or even decorative elements) that makes then deviations of the initial Type.

6.3. Interflows between Tradition and Innovation

Generally we can associate Tradition to Vernacular Architecture and Innovation to Erudite Architecture. Between these, where can we attach Popular Architecture? Although Tradition no longer regulates architecture's main features, it remains in the continuous adaptation that the Type suffers in order to still respond to uses and mores that linger in local cultures with more or less defined boundaries. In the present case study Innovation is evident in the introduction of a Type that has its image as one of its main features.

The deviations that occur in the variable spatial matrix or in the relation established between building and public accesses (roads, trails) can influence the social behaviour among dwellers and the whole community. But it has no influence in its subsistence, since the "initial Module" is only part of an organism composed by many volumes, like farming facilities or cattle raising (even if these annexes are absent – always will be – in the City Hall's licences).

This Module or Type is therefore part of the already mentioned process where a determined culture tries to attach itself to other "upscale" social rankings through the use of its signs and significant (which are signs, but deprived of their significance, meaning – being the immigrant house an even more obvious example).

So, in our present research, Innovation can be related to the introduction of a new Image, besides a correct understanding of its real symbolism. On the other hand, it's another kind of Innovation, different from the one we usually associate with Erudite Architecture. We are talking about "introducing something new in a pre-existence" rather than "renovate, invent, create"²² (while always being aware that in the Erudite's domain the interaction of cultures is constant).

²² "Erudito" (2012), In Dicionário Priberam da Língua Portuguesa, Priberam Informática, S.A. Disponível em: <http://www.priberam.pt/dlpo/> [01.2013]

6.4. Other Concepts

We can conclude that there is a difference among the presented concepts architectural types, more obvious in the context of Vernacular and Erudite architecture, but more subtle when referring to Vernacular and Popular manifestations. This subtlety can be assumed to the fact Popular Architecture may be "born" or "created" from Vernacular one, through the addition of Erudite elements (in our presented case studies – if two vernacular cultures come across that also results in Popular manifestations, since borders have been crossed and innovation has been introduced).

If we assume that Vernacular Architecture aims for an erudite identification through the use of its Significances, we can also verify that the opposite can also be true: an Architect who has the purpose of identifying its projects to its surroundings it will make use of some of the Vernacular and/or Popular characteristics of its Architecture. These are, putting it into a very simple and concise matter, the concept behind the already mentioned Kenneth Frampton's "Critical Contextualism"²³. Something that, according to him, began when the Modern Movement proved to be "unidentifiable" for most people as "their own" Models and Types, and the Modernist dogmas started to be questioned.

Proposals like the Josep Antoni Coderch and Manuel Valls' "Casa Ugalde" (1952) of, or Álvaro Siza Vieira's "Boa Nova Tea House" (1963), in its own personal way, include elements from the local vernacular and popular architecture, also paying attention to other features like the landscape, making their proposal belong, in more than one way, to the site where they were built and conceived for.

This "reverse" process although it needs to be mentioned here, has enough information and matter of discussion to constitute an entire article by itself, and can and should be the next step for further researches in the present field of knowledge.

7. Conclusion

The need to create a lexicon in Architecture that allows the researcher or practitioner to use a series of common meanings lead to the present article. Meaning that, to obtain coherence in a dialogue about the vernacular/popular subject, the use of terms and their significance must be the same to each author.

Of course we must be aware that the degree of "certainty" among these concepts must have some leeway, just to avoid dogmas that can be as harmful as the absence of consensus. Also, what we can define as Vernacular in its more "pure" or "virginal" state (devoid of any type of external influence) may have occurred only in a very distant past (or still in a lost tribe in Amazonia...) as some kind of knowledge trade always happens in some way...

Frampton, when defining "Critical Regionalism" defines local or national culture as something abstract or paradoxical, because all civilizations seem to have been born from a cross-fertilization, where the local landscape must, without a doubt, result from the split of the regional with the universal culture. Nevertheless he doesn't deny the existence of a Vernacular fashion, since he doesn't make clear the origins of the specific civilization that fertilized the original expression (implicitly recognizing a "beginning").

All said, that doesn't turn the present effort to categorize and classify the above mentioned

²³ Frampton, K. (1996), *Historia crítica de la arquitectura moderna*. Editorial Gustavo Gili, S.A., pp.318-332, ISBN 84-252-1628-1

Frampton, K. (1983) *Towards a critical regionalism: six points for an architecture of resistance*. In, Foster, H. (ed). *Postmodern Culture*. London; Pluto Press, 1985, pp.16-30., ISBN-10: 0745300030

architectural expressions useless, since behind all efforts among learning and communication there is a need to make use of a common vocabulary. In our present and contemporary architectural context where abstract formal features become the face of a theoretical crisis (where words seem to be the main form of communicating visually incomprehensible shapes) there is a need to search for a more figurative architecture. Therefore the need to create a lexicon in order to proceed to a typological research among our surrounding's references becomes necessary. And the determination among architects to make their proposals "belong" to a specific physical and cultural area is connected to this idea of using "references", always linked to an idea of "past".

Efforts have been made to identify regional or local Types and Models (in all the above quoted examples, using "Arquitectura Popular em Portugal" as the main reference), but it is undeniable that our (present) Past was the Present situation for those who worked on the previous researches. And the references that nowadays have become our "local" expression may not be the previous "Vernacular Architecture" once collected, but the "Popular" that resulted from a more and more connected society.

To Marieta Dá Mesquita, no longer among us, I dedicate this proposal or intent of understanding our rural legacy, due to her qualities as a Tutor and a friend that would made her the perfect companion to further "adventures".